

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20595026

Physical Facilities as Predictor of Students' Academic Achievement in Colleges of Education in North Central Zone of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The Nigeria certificate in education, being a major sector of teacher's education, generally aims at producing teachers with high personal and professional discipline and integrity, teachers who are dedicated with appropriate knowledge, skills and attitudes that would facilitate easy achievement of the national goals. To achieve this, it is expected that teaching and learning should be done with the use of physical facilities. This study investigated physical facilities as predictors of students' academic achievement in college of education in north central Nigeria. The investigation was confined to classroom facilities, language laboratory facilities and utilization of facilities on student's achievement for five academic sessions (2007/2008 to 2011/2012) in English language, Mathematics and Integrated science. The study employed two designs, survey research and ex-post-facto, covering an accessible population of 39,220 NCE (3) from the (14) fourteen Colleges of Education in North Central Zone. The sample size of 3,800 NCE (3) from the area of study was proportionately selected for each of the colleges under study. Data was collected through questionnaire and proforma and were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and Multiple Regression. Three research questions were raised and three hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that physical facilities are predictors of students' academic achievement especially if well utilized by students. The paper also recommended that, all colleges should ensure that their classrooms have all the facilities and language laboratories are available to a higher extent to improve on students' academic achievement in the colleges.

Keywords: Physical Facilities, Student's Achievement, Nigeria Certificate in Education

INTRODUCTION

Every society attaches importance to education because it is regarded as a panacea for many evils, the key to solving the various problems of life. Higher education in particular, is the education given after secondary education in universities, colleges of education, polytechnics and monotechnics in addition to those institutions offering correspondence courses. It is fundamental to the construction of knowledge, economy and society in all nations. To achieve this goal, teachers need to use a wide variety of physical facilities which can enrich the learning environment and influence students' academic achievement. The availability and utilization of physical facilities in education brings about fruitful learning outcomes since it's a predictor of students' academic achievement (Okorie, 2001).

Physical facilities refers to the school plant, that is, the school buildings, classrooms, libraries, laboratories, recreational facilities, toilet facilities, offices and other materials that would likely a predictor of students towards learning. Physical facilities are germane to effective teaching/learning and academic achievement of students. In support of this, Hallak in Akomolafe and Adesua (2016), identifies

facilities as the main factor contributing to academic achievement in the school system. The physical facilities provided in colleges influence not only the education provided to students but also aspects of student's motivation to learn and consequently the educational outcomes. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) states that unavailability of facilities hinders instruction and lower students' achievement (OECD, 2007). In addition, inequalities in students' academic achievement often reflect disparities in the utilization of physical facilities in institutions of learning (OECD, 2008). In some education systems, there are concerns that colleges not only lack the physical facilities to meet the educational requirements of their students, but that colleges may have fewer physical facilities with which to provide instruction to their students (OECD, 2008). In colleges, there are a wide variety of physical facilities that are directly or indirectly related to students' academic achievement.

For the production of adequate and quality teachers, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2012) states clearly that the teacher is the king-pin of quality in education. Since education is undeniably the primary tool for the overall development of society, Teacher Education has to occupy a position of pre-eminence in the planning and organization of the modern society. This in turn demands that the Nigerian people and government make both teaching and teacher education a very attractive professional pursuit. Expectedly, the objectives of Teacher Education in Nigeria among others, includes:

1. Production of well-motivated teachers with high personal and professional discipline, integrity and competence for all the levels of the educational system;
2. Preparation of teachers with appreciable expertise in curriculum planning, development and delivery, as well as competence in research, guidance and counseling;
3. Production of professionals who can combine the use of conventional teaching strategies and the worlds' unfolding Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the generation and imparting of knowledge, attitudes and skills;
4. Continuous preparation and upgrading of teachers who can stand out for their professional competence, sense of social responsibility and commitment, to function effectively as constructive socio-economic, moral and spiritual change agents needed to promote goodwill, peace and progress not only in the country, but also in the world of the 21st Century. (NCCE, 2012)

The Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) programme, being a major sector of teacher education, generally aims at producing teachers with high personal and professional discipline and integrity, teachers who are dedicated, with appropriate knowledge, skills and attitudes that would facilitate easy achievement of the national goals spelt out above. And to achieve this, it is expected that all the educational programmes offered in all colleges be taught by the use of physical facilities that are important to the effective teaching and learning of such programmes mounted. This is in accordance with the laid down standards of the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2012). Since physical facilities and educational objectives are closely inter-dependent, it is assumed that they represent a learning environment that may have multiple influences on students' academic achievement. Just as we need shelter to protect domestic activities from the elements, and to provide security, so must we provide shelter to education.

The Federal Government of Nigeria in recognition of the relevance of physical facilities in institutions of learning, has approved guidelines for the establishment of higher institutions of learning in Nigeria. Relevant excerpts from the National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions (Amendment Decree No. 9 of 1993) state clearly that, the Federal Government or its accredited agency shall ascertain and be satisfied that:

1. The applicant has supplied a concrete and guaranteed source of financial support for the College of Education to the tune of N50 million over a period of 5 years.
2. A proposed institution shall have a clearly spelt out master plan for infrastructural and programme development for at least 20 to 25 years which shall make adequate provision for:
 - (a) Plan space and fixed final assets;
 - (b) Minimum land area of 25 hectares for a College of Education, in a salutary site.

The site distance from an urban complex shall take into account availability of municipal services, including water, transportation, private accommodation, communication and others in its community. The library, laboratory and workshop facilities including instructional tools and consumables, shall be adequate and there shall be long-range plans for sustaining them. Academic achievement also denotes the knowledge attained and skill developed in the school subject, usually designed by test scores. The level of achieving is how far a student succeeds in a particular examination or standardized test.

Commenting on students' academic achievement from Colleges of Education, Owoeye and Yara (2011) identify poor and inadequate physical facilities, obsolete teaching techniques, overcrowded classrooms, among others, as factors that predict the low academic achievement. Isa, Zahari and Yusoff (2015) identify some of the problems that predict the low academic achievement among students in colleges of education to include: lack of infrastructure, students' overpopulation, frequent strikes by both the academic and supporting staff. Adeyemi (2014) identifies factors like poor lighting, lack of school calendar stability and to a lesser extent, teaching methods, as significant predictors of students' academic achievement in South-Western colleges of education in Nigeria.

In a related development, Oladejo, (2011) observed that students who were taught with the improvised laboratory facilities achieved statistically significantly higher scores in their exams compared to those who were taught with a conventional method.

To guild the study three research questions and hypotheses were formulated

1. to what extent is the classroom a predictor of students' academic achievement in colleges of education?
2. to what extent do language laboratory serve as a predictor of students' academic achievement in colleges of education?
3. to what extent do students utilize the physical facilities in colleges of education?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null Hypotheses are formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Classroom facilities do not significantly predict students' academic achievement in colleges of education in North central zone of Nigeria
2. Language laboratory facilities do not significantly predict students' academic achievement in colleges of education in North central zone of Nigeria
3. There is no significant prediction of students' utilization of physical facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted survey research design. Also an ex-post facto design was also used because of the involvement of students results This is because the researcher could not manipulate the scores of the result, This study covered the North Central Zone of Nigeria, which comprises six (6) states and the FCT. The states are Benue, Kogi, Nassarawa, Kwara, Niger, and Plateau, The population for the study comprises 39,220 NCE (3) students from fourteen (14) Colleges of Education in North Central Zone Nigeria with federal and state status, The information was obtained from Digest of Statistics on Colleges of Education and other NCE-Awarding Institutions in Nigeria (NCCE, 2015). The sample size for the study was 3,800 students from the total population of 39,220 NCE (3) The sample size of seven (7) Colleges of Education was drawn from the total population of fourteen (14) public Colleges of Education in North Central Zone of Nigeria as at the time of this study. The sample was selected using multi stage sampling technique. Two instruments were used in collecting data. The first was self-developed questionnaire titled: Physical Facilities as Predictor of Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire (PFPSAAQ). In order to ensure that the instruments measure what they ought to measure were validated by two management experts. the validated instrument were administered to thirty (30) respondents, The Cronbach Alpha.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Demographic analysis of Students’ academic achievement results in the sampled Colleges of Education in North Central Zone of Nigeria between 2007-2012 academic sessions.

Year	SA		Dist.		Cred		Merit		Pass		LP		Fail	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
2007/2008	6110	3657	53	0.9	468	7.7	1689	27.6	1052	17.2	211	3.5	2343	38.3
2008/2009	6519	3984	95	1.5	575	8.8	1784	27.4	1127	17.3	327	5.0	2431	37.3
2009/2010	6866	4059	131	1.9	548	8.0	1728	25.2	1203	17.5	438	6.4	2662	38.8
2010/2011	7626	2987	68	0.9	403	5.3	1445	18.9	741	9.7	345	4.5	4503	59.0
2011/2012	8875	5000	85	1.0	758	8.5	1943	21.9	1705	19.2	553	6.2	3768	42.5
Average	7199	3937	86	1.2	550	7.7	1718	24.2	1166	16.2	375	5.1	3141	43.2

Figure i: Graph showing Students’ academic achievement results in the sampled Colleges of Education in North Central Zone of Nigeria between 2007-2012 academic sessions

Table 1, and figure 1 presents the demographic analysis of Students’ academic achievement results in the sampled Colleges of Education in North Central Zone of Nigeria between 2007/2008 to 2011/2012 academic sessions. The result shows that 43.2% of the students admitted during the period under study failed. On the average, 1.2% of the total enrolment from 2007/2008 to 2011/2012 had distinction, 7.7% passed at credit level, 24.2% had merit while 16.2%, had pass and 5.1% had lower pass respectively. The bar chart in figure1. reveals that the level of students' academic achievement in colleges of education North Central Zone of Nigeria between 2007/2008 to 2011/2012 academic sessions is low.

Question 1: To what extent do classroom facilities predict students' academic achievement in colleges of Education?

Table 2: Descriptive analysis showing the extent classroom facilities predict students' academic achievement in colleges of Education?

S/N	ITEMS	HE	ME	LE	NE	Mean	SD
1.	Comfortable classrooms influence students' academic achievement	1738 (45.7%)	1477 (38.9%)	585 (15.4%)	-	3.30	0.72
2.	Sufficient lighting in classroom improves students' ability to see clearly.	2173 (57.2%)	1077 (28.3%)	474 (12.5%)	76 (2.0%)	3.41	0.78
3.	Well-ventilated classrooms provide high air quality that improves students' concentration in the classroom.	2173 (57.2%)	1153 (30.0%)	398 (10.5%)	76 (2.0%)	3.43	0.76
4.	Proper desk arrangements in the classroom give students' access to comfortable seats during lectures.	2173 (57.2%)	1153 (30.3%)	398 (10.5%)	76 (2.0%)	3.43	0.76
5.	Sound amplification system enhances clarity of lecturers' instruction.	2173 (57.2%)	1153 (30.3%)	398 (10.5%)	76 (2.0%)	3.43	0.76
Average		2086 (54.9%)	1203 (31.7%)	451 (11.9%)	60 (1.6%)	3.40	0.29

Source: Field survey, 2017

Figure ii: Graph showing the extent classroom facilities predict students' academic achievement in colleges of Education?

The result in table ii and figure ii revealed the prediction of classroom facilities on students' academic achievement where on high extent of 54.9% follows by 31.7%, 11.9% and no prediction is 1.6% with the respective numbers 2086, 1203, 451 and 60

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant prediction of classroom facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education.

In testing the hypothesis, scores on classroom facilities and students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education were computed and analyzed using statistical package involving Regression statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Regression analysis showing the prediction of classroom facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.138	.020		56.795	.000
Classroom facilities	.416	.010	.651	41.670	.000

Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

Multiple R = 0.651

Multiple R² = 0.424

Adjusted R² = 0.424

F = 1736.394

Probability = p<0.05

The following regression can be derived from Table 6

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where

b = Regression Weight Coefficient

a = Constant (other variables other than X)

The regression of relationship between the dependent and independent variables can therefore be given as follow:

$$Y = 1.138 + 0.416X$$

Table 3 shows that there is significant prediction of classroom facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education. (t=41.670*, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected.

This shows that there is a significant, high and positive multiple correlation between the predictor variable - classroom facilities and students' academic achievement (r=0.651, p<0.05). This implies that the predictor variable is factor that can exert students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education. The calculated $F_{1,3798} = 1736.394$ is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the relationship between the predictor variable and students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education is statistically significant at 0.05 level. The value of the coefficient of determination ($r^2=0.424$) indicates that the predictor variable explained 42.4% ($r^2 \times 100$) of the total variance in students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education while the remaining 57.6% unexplained variation is largely due to other variable that can account for students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education.

Question 2: To what extent do language laboratory facilities predict students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education?

Table 4: Descriptive analysis showing the prediction of language laboratory facilities on students' academic performance in Colleges of Education

S/N	ITEMS	HE	ME	LE	NE	Mean	SD
1.	Language laboratories predict students learning of a language.	2240 (58.9%)	1162 (30.6%)	398 (10.5%)	-	3.49	0.68
2.	Using Language laboratories helps students perform better in speaking skills.	2163 (56.9%)	1239 (32.6%)	398 (10.5%)	-	3.47	0.68
3.	Language laboratories develop students' pronunciation in the language they are learning.	2014 (53.0%)	1388 (36.5%)	398 (10.5%)	-	3.43	0.68
4.	Language laboratories provide more interactive activities for speaking skill.	1717 (45.2%)	1608 (42.3%)	398 (10.5%)	77 (2.0%)	3.31	0.74
5.	Language laboratories help students practice the features of connected speech (stress and intonation).	1639 (43.1%)	1104 (29.1%)	980 (25.8%)	77 (2.0%)	3.13	0.87
Average		1955 (51.4%)	1300 (34.2%)	514 (13.6%)	31 (0.8%)	3.36	0.41

Source: Field survey, 2017

Figure 4: Graph showing the prediction of language laboratory facilities on students' academic performance in Colleges of Education

The table 4 and fig 4 revealed that 1955 (51.4%) students indicated high extent to five items; 1300 (34.2%) to the moderate extent of the five items, 514 (13.6%) to the low extent of the items while 31 (0.8%) students show no extent.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant prediction of language laboratory facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to language laboratory facilities and students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education were computed and subsequently subjected to statistical analysis with statistical package involving Regression statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 5: Regression showing the prediction of language laboratory facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.589	.011		142.601	.000
Language laboratory facilities	.045	.004	.279	11.771	.000

*p<0.05

Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

Multiple R = 0.279

Multiple R² = 0.078

Adjusted R² = 0.077

F = 138.566

Probability = p<0.05

The following regression can be derived from Table 8

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where

b = Regression Weight Coefficient

a = Constant (other variables other than X)

The multiple regressions relationship between the dependent and independent variables can therefore be given as follow: $Y = 1.589 +$

Table 5 shows that there is significant prediction of language laboratory facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education. (t=11.771*, P<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected.

This shows that there is a significant, positive but low multiple correlation between the predictor variable - language laboratory facilities and students' academic achievement (r=0.279, p<0.05). This implies that the predictor variable is a factor that can predict students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education. The calculated $F_{1,3798} = 138.566$ is significant at 0.05 level confirming the significance of the correlation. The value of the coefficient of determination ($r^2=0.078$) indicates that the predictor variable accounted for about 7.8% ($r^2 \times 100$) of the total variance in students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education while the remaining 92.2% unexplained variation is largely due to other variables outside the regression model.

Question 3: To what extent do students utilize the physical facilities in Colleges of Education in North Central Zone?

Table 6: Descriptive analysis showing the extent of students' utilization of available physical facilities Colleges of Education.

S/N	ITEMS	HE	ME	LE	NE	Mean	SD
1.	All students in your college learn in classroom with facilities	134 (3.5%)	1227 (32.3%)	1839 (48.4%)	600 (15.8%)	2.24	0.75
2.	All language students in your college learn in Language laboratory	102 (2.7%)	1772 (46.6%)	1402 (36.9%)	524 (13.8%)	1.72	0.75
3.	All students in your college learn with the use of libraries	102 (2.7%)	1247 (32.8%)	1565 (41.2%)	886 (23.3%)	2.15	0.80
4.	All Physical and Health Education students in your college learn in Campus recreation facilities	303 (8.0%)	1155 (30.4%)	1754 (46.2%)	588 (15.5%)	2.31	0.83
5.	All science students in your college learn in Science Laboratories	102 (2.7%)	1448 (38.1%)	1583 (41.7%)	667 (17.6%)	2.15	0.77
Average		149 (3.9%)	1370 (36.1%)	1629 (42.9%)	652 (17.1%)	2.27	0.39

Source: field survey 2017

Table 3 and Figure 2 reveal that 134(3.5%) of the total sample indicated high extent regarding students learning with the facilities, 1227(32.3%) moderate extent, 1839(48.4%) low extent and 600(15.8%) no

extent. On whether all language students in the colleges learn in Language laboratory, 102(2.7%) indicated high extent, 1772(46.6%) moderate extent, 1402(36.9%) low extent and 524(13.8%) no extent. 102(2.7%) indicated that all students in their college learn with the use of libraries to a high extent that, 1247(32.8%) reported moderate extent, 1565(41.2%) low extent and 886(23.3%) no extent. On whether all Physical and Health Education students in their colleges learn in Campus recreation facilities, 303(8%) indicated high extent, 1155(30.4%) moderate extent, 1754(46.2%) low extent, 588(15.5%) no extent. 102(2.7%) of the total sample indicated that science students in their colleges learn in Science Laboratories to an high extent, 1448(38.1%) moderate extent, 1583(41.7%) low extent and 667(17.7%) no extent.

On the average, 149(3.9%) reported that extent students utilized the available physical facilities in Colleges of Education in North Central Zone to an high extent, 1370(36.1%) moderate extent, 1629(42.9%) low extent and 652(17.1%) no extent. With a mean score of 2.27 and standard deviation of 0.39, it implies that the extent of students' utilization of the available physical facilities in Colleges of Education in North Central Zone is low.

Figure 6: Graph showing the extent of students' utilization of available physical facilities in Colleges of Education in North Central Zone

Table 3 and Figure 2 reveal that 600(15.8%) of the total sample indicated high extent regarding students learning with the facilities, , 1839(48.4%) moderate extent, 1227(32.3%) low extent and 134(3.5%) no extent. On whether all language students in the colleges learn in Language laboratory, 524(13.8%) indicated high extent, 1402(36.9%) moderate extent, 1772(46.6%) low extent and 102(2.7%) no extent. 886(23.3%) indicated that all students in their college learn with the use of libraries to a high extent that, 1565(41.2%) reported moderate extent, 1247(32.8%) low extent and 102(2.7%) no extent. On whether all Physical and Health Education students in their colleges learn in Campus recreation facilities, 588(15.5%) indicated high extent, 1754(46.2%) moderate extent, 1155(30.4%) low extent, 303(8.0%) no extent. 667(17.6%) of the total sample indicated that science students in their colleges learn in Science Laboratories to an high extent, 1583(41.7%) moderate extent, 1448(38.1%) low extent and 102(2.7%) no extent.

On the average, 653(17.2%) reported that extent students utilized the available physical facilities in Colleges of Education in North Central Zone to an high extent, 1629(42.9%) moderate extent, 1370(36.1%) low extent and 148(3.8%) no extent. With a mean score of 2.73 and standard deviation of 0.39, it implies that the extent of students' utilization of the available physical facilities in Colleges of Education in North Central Zone is moderate.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant prediction of students' utilization of physical facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to students' utilization of the required physical facilities and students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education were computed and analyzed with statistical package involving Regression statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 7: Regression showing the prediction of students' utilization of physical facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.486	.026		57.239	.000
Utilization of physical facilities	.018	.002	.155	9.701	.000

Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

Multiple R = 0.155

Multiple R² = 0.024

Adjusted R² = 0.024

F = 94.110

Probability = p<0.05

The following regression can be derived from Table 4

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where

b = Regression Weight Coefficient

a = Constant (other variables other than X₁-X₁)

The regression analysis of relationship between the dependent and independent variables can therefore be given as follow:

$$Y = 1.486 + 0.018X$$

Table 7 shows that there is significant prediction of students' utilization of the required physical facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education. (t=9.701*, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant prediction of students' utilization of the required physical facilities on students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education.

The table reveals that there is a significant positive, but very low multiple correlation between the predictor variable - utilization of physical facilities and students' academic achievement (r=0.155, p<0.05). This implies that the predictor variable is factor that can exert predict students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education. The F_{1,3798} =94.110) is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the correlation between predictor variable and students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education is very low but statistically significant at 0.05 level. The value of the coefficient of determination (r²=0.024) indicates that the predictor variable only accounted for 2.4% (r² X 100) of the observed variance in students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education while the remaining 97.6% unexplained variation can be attributed to other variables that can account for students' academic achievement in Colleges of Education.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the empirical findings, the study concluded that, physical facilities are predictors of students' academic achievement especially if well utilized by students, academic achievement will be highly improved, and this may also improve the quality of teachers produced from Colleges of Education to teach at the levels of primary and secondary school levels.

The paper also recommended that, all colleges should ensure that their classrooms have all the facilities like, enough lighting, ventilation system, desk arrangement, Classroom Amplification system, among others to a higher extent to improve students' academic achievement and all colleges should ensure that a language laboratories are available to a higher extent to improve on students' academic achievement in the colleges.

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